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Phosphodiesterase induction during chemotherapy resistance.

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Phosphodiesterase induction during chemotherapy resistance included PDE7B activation.

Citations

1. Hetman, J.M., Soderling, S.H., Glavas, N.A. and Beavo, J.A., 2000. Cloning and characterization of PDE7B, a cAMP-specific phosphodiesterase. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 97(1), pp.472-476.